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**Title: "Existence and Non-Existence as Quantum Probability:
A Probability-Based Alternative to Schrödinger's Cat".**

Abstract:

In this scientific conceptual note, that presents an analogy of the Superposition principle in Quantum Mechanics using a Probabilistic viewpoint. We take Quantum Mechanics to the Probability Theory of the classical world where the two different states being Existence and Non-Existence of the particle exactly determine the other. It is nearly the same concept as the Schrödinger's Cat thought experiment which represent the action of an observer causing reality to become just one possibility. This point of view intends to translate the Quantum Superposition into a simple idea and might also open a new view of the measurement problem.

Introduction:

Quantum Mechanics that's challenges our Classical understanding of reality. Introducing concepts such as Quantum Superposition, Probability and Wave-Particle Duality. Schrödinger's Cat Experiment is a thought Experiment that proposed by Erwin Schrödinger. Illustrates the paradox of Quantum Superposition—suggesting that a system can exist in multiple states until Measured. This paradox raises fundamental questions about Existence and Observation in Quantum Mechanics.

In this paper, we propose an alternative method: that Existence and Non-Existence as a Probabilistic States governed by fundamental principle of Probability Theory. Specifically, we examine the idea that Existence (E) and Non-Existence ($\neg E$) can be expressed within a Probability framework where their Sum remains Unity (1).

This formulation aligns with Classical Probability Law and provides an alternative way to understand Quantum Uncertainty. By studying parallel between Probability Theory and Quantum Mechanics. We explore whether existence itself can be modelled as a probabilistic event rather than a binary state dictated solely by Observation/Measurement.

This approach seeks to provide a conceptual bridge between Classical Probability and Quantum Mechanics, that shows a fresh interpretation that could complement or extend existing models of Quantum Measurement and reality. Through mathematical reasoning and thought experiments, we analyse

how this perspective aligns with Quantum Principles and its potential implications for Fundamental Physics.

Classical Analogy: A Fair or Unbiased coin:

$$P(\text{Head})=1/2,$$

$$P(\text{Tail})=1/2.$$

Therefore, the Total Probability is:

$$P(\text{Head})+P(\text{Tail})=1$$

Similarly, we propose that the concept of Existence(E) and Non-Existence(-E) can be modelled with equal Probability:

$$P(E)+P(-E)=1.$$

This representation shows Observation or Measurement.

A system could be equally in state of Existence or Non-Existence like a Fair or Unbiased Coin.

Quantum Interpretation: Superposition of E and -E

Before Measurement, a Quantum Particle is not in one specific state but in a superposition of possible states.

By Drawing from analogy:

A Quantum system is the superposition of Existence and Non – Existence.

This shows the idea that reality is not fixed until observed.

Observation acts as a 'collapse' mechanism, that select one of the equal probable outcomes.

This can be notated as:

$$\Psi = \alpha|E\rangle + \beta|\neg E\rangle$$

Where in this simplified analogy is

$$|\alpha|^2 = |\beta|^2 = \frac{1}{2}.$$

Connection to Schrödinger Cat

In Schrödinger thought experiment, the cat is described as both Alive or Dead. A Quantum Superposition of two macroscopically distinct states.

In this analogy:

"Alive" \leftrightarrow "Existence" (Head)

"Dead" \leftrightarrow "Non-Existence" (Tail)

Measurement and Observation (Interpretation)

From the perspective, Quantum Measurement is like checking whether a Coin (Fair or Unbiased) has landed as Head or Tail. That's verify whether Exists or does Not Exist.

Before Observation the system is in a superposition state. Both in $|E\rangle$ and $|\neg E\rangle$, co-exist in a single waveform.

$$\Psi = \alpha|E\rangle + \beta|\neg E\rangle$$

After Observation the system collapse into one of its states, either $|E\rangle$ or $|\neg E\rangle$ with probability determined by $|\alpha|^2$ and $|\beta|^2$.

In the same way, a Coin (Fair or Unbiased) is determined to be Head or Tail when Observed, the Wavefunction is collapse into single.

This simplified model helps to conceptualize the Quantum idea that reality is not determined until it is Observed.

Implications and Further Thoughts

Quantum Superposition is typically visually presented in this model, where the Classical Probability is a simple and understandable method. This is not a full fix to the measurement problem but will definitely help to understand the foundation for the new way of interdisciplinary interpretation of the Quantum world.

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